

Theoretical Fits to Second Harmonic Generation in KDP vs. Angle of Incidence*

Anson Kost

*Physics Department, University of Arizona
Tucson, Arizona 85721*

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In 2nd harmonic generation (SHG), a 2nd harmonic light wave is generated with twice the frequency of a fundamental pump wave in a nonlinear medium. The effect is a result of polarization terms of 2nd order in the electric field components.

The beam of a 1040 nm pulsed fiber laser was focused into a 0.5 mm long KDP crystal to produce a 2nd harmonic beam (which can be seen in Fig. 5). The intensity of the 2nd harmonic was measured as a function of the angle of incidence of the 1040 nm beam on the crystal face. The results were compared to predictions of a theoretical model based on simple fundamental nonlinear optical theory and calculated numerically using Python. The measurements and fitted theoretical curves are graphed in Figs. 7-11.

The fit was reasonable for all data and good for the most accurate set of data taken (method C, Figs. 7-9), which took into account the variations in the output power of the laser over longer periods of time. The results indicate that the nonlinear optical theory and approximations used to create the fits describe the experimental situation well, and motivate similar explorations in sum frequency generation (SFG) and sum difference generation (SFD) phenomena as well as in the linear and nonlinear optical properties of media.

Usage: PHYS 382 creative project, and for anything it might help with.

I. INTRODUCTION

2nd harmonic generation (SHG) is an intrinsically nonlinear optical process in which the product of the oscillating components of a fundamental light wave traveling in a nonlinear material give rise to harmonic polarization terms and the generation of 2nd harmonic radiation at double the frequency of the fundamental light. SHG cannot be achieved in linear media because it depends on the 2nd order dependence of the polarization on the electric field components. High intensity fundamental radiation is also needed for the 2nd order terms to become significant (see Ref. [1] for a case of low intensity SHG). Because of this need, SHG was not discovered until one year after the invention of the laser. The discovery was made by Peter Franken et al.[2], and the theory carried out a year later by Bloembergen and Pershan[3]. (SHG also requires a nonsymmetric crystal structure since the 2nd order response stays the same under inversion of the sign of both contributing components, so that it has an inherent directional preference.)

The generation of 2nd harmonic waves, and the generalization thereof for 2nd order effects which consists of sum frequency generation (SFG) and difference frequency generation (DFG), is now widely used in a range of applications for the production of radiation at frequencies that would otherwise be difficult or impossible to achieve. A typical case is the one we demonstrate, in which a moderate intensity IR laser beam with a wavelength near 1064 nm is passed through a nonlinear crystal such as KDP

and generates a green 2nd harmonic beam. Most green lasers use SHG in this way to create their green light[4][5]. Recently, poorly designed green laser pointers have appeared in the consumer market which utilize SHG but fail to remove the higher intensity IR fundamental beam, leading to a misleadingly dangerous product[6][7].

SHG can also be used in medical imaging of cells[8]. For example, the arrangements of collagen in cancerous cells lead to nonlinear optical effects and a noticeable 2nd harmonic response from the cell at certain fundamental frequencies[9].

In the current experiment, we aim to investigate the applicability of the fundamental theory of nonlinear optics, from a first principles approach, to a simple practical experimental setup. In particular, we measure the dependence of the (520 nm) 2nd harmonic intensity produced by a KDP crystal on the angle of incidence of the (1040 nm) fundamental beam, and compare the results to a curve predicted by the theory. In this situation, the nonlinear process of phase matching along with the nonlinear analogies to the linear processes of refraction and reflection must be taken into account in the theory.

The final data and the corresponding theoretical predictions are shown in Figs. 7-11. Fit parameters and estimates of background radiation obtained from the fits are listed below each figure.

The theory fits well to the measurements, and the results are promising for a first-time, simplified fundamental approach to SHG.

II. THEORY

Many of the following derivations paraphrase or are generalizations of those by Baldwin[10] (Ch. 4).

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A. Wave Equation

By taking the curl of the Maxwell-Faraday equation

$$\nabla \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) = \nabla \times (-\dot{\mathbf{B}})$$

and using for the general curl of \mathbf{B}

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mu_0(\varepsilon_0 \dot{\mathbf{E}} + \mathbf{J}),$$

a wave equation is obtained for \mathbf{E} :

$$\nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{E} + \mu_0 \varepsilon_0 \ddot{\mathbf{E}} = -\mu_0 \dot{\mathbf{J}}.$$

(In the approximation of a linear medium where the refractive indices also vary slowly in space compared to the electric field, the double curl of the field above reduces to the negative of the Laplacian of the field.)

In the case of media with only an electric dipole response described by the polarization \mathbf{P} , and no free current, $\mathbf{J} = \dot{\mathbf{P}}$ and this wave equation takes the form

$$\nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{E} + \mu_0 \varepsilon_0 \ddot{\mathbf{E}} = -\mu_0 \ddot{\mathbf{P}}. \quad (1)$$

B. SHG as a Perturbation

1. Nonlinear Effects as Perturbations

\mathbf{P} is a function of \mathbf{E} whose components can be expanded as a polynomial in terms of products of powers of components of \mathbf{E} . In linear media, only the 1st degree terms survive so that

$$\mathbf{P}^{(1)} = \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\chi}^{(1)} \cdot \mathbf{E},$$

and the solutions to eq. (1) are waves propagating with speeds and polarizations given by the refractive indices $n_{ij} = \sqrt{1 + \chi_{ij}}$. (The waves that propagate coherently in a given direction are polarized along one of two axes with a corresponding refractive index, both determined by the "index ellipsoid" representing n_{ij} .)

For examining the effects of the 2nd order terms of \mathbf{P} ,

$$\mathbf{P}^{(2)} = \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\chi}^{(2)} \cdot \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E}, \quad (2)$$

the 1st order polarization above is grouped with the left hand side of eq. (1) so that the 1st order solutions are solutions to the homogeneous equation, and the 2nd order polarization becomes the inhomogeneous term. In this way, 2nd order nonlinear effects are treated as perturbations to the solutions for linear media.

2. Treatment of SHG

In the case of 2nd harmonic generation from a fundamental wave of frequency ω , the fundamental and its

generated harmonic are treated as separately propagating waves, each satisfying the wave equation with a respective inhomogeneous coupling term. The 2nd order coupling polarization (eq. (2)) at the frequency of the 2nd harmonic is a result of addition of the frequencies of two components of the fundamental wave, while the coupling term for the fundamental arises from the frequency difference between components of the fundamental and harmonic waves. Written out, the fundamental field satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} c^2 \nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{E}^{(\omega)} - \omega^2 (\mathbf{E}^{(\omega)} + \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\chi}^{(1,\omega)} \cdot \mathbf{E}^{(\omega)}) \\ = \omega^2 \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\chi}^{(2,\omega)} \cdot \mathbf{E}^{(\omega)} \cdot \mathbf{E}^{(2\omega)}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

and the 2nd harmonic field satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} c^2 \nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{E}^{(2\omega)} - (2\omega)^2 (\mathbf{E}^{(2\omega)} + \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\chi}^{(1,2\omega)} \cdot \mathbf{E}^{(2\omega)}) \\ = (2\omega)^2 \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\chi}^{(2,2\omega)} \cdot \mathbf{E}^{(\omega)} \cdot \mathbf{E}^{(\omega)}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

C. Plane Wave SHG

In the following subsections, the fundamental and harmonic waves are assumed to be linearly polarized plane waves.

1. Low Efficiency Phase Matching

When the amount of energy converted to the 2nd harmonic is small, the fundamental wave is approximately unaffected by the 2nd order effects (so that the coupling term in eq. (3) may be omitted). The coupling term in eq. (4) then also oscillates with uniform amplitude. This source term has double the fundamental frequency and a wavevector that is the sum of the wavevectors of the two contributing components of the fundamental.

The solution to eq. (4) becomes an integral of plane waves emitted by the source polarization at all points. The harmonic travels with frequency 2ω and a wavevector \mathbf{k}_2 collinear to the source wavevector $\mathbf{k}_1 + \mathbf{k}'_1$. At a depth $u = \mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{k}_2$ in the medium in the direction of propagation, the integral of all these traveling waves from a depth less than u gives for the 2nd harmonic field

$$\mathbf{E}^{(2\omega)}(u) = i \frac{1 - e^{i\Delta k u}}{\Delta k} e^{i(k_2 u - 2\omega t)} \mathbf{q},$$

where $\Delta k \equiv k_2 - |\mathbf{k}_1 + \mathbf{k}'_1|$ is the difference between the actual and phase matched 2nd harmonic wavenumbers and \mathbf{q} is a constant vector characterizing the strength (and direction) of the 2nd harmonic's response due to the source polarization. The corresponding real oscillation is proportional to

$$\frac{\sin(\Delta k u)}{\Delta k}. \quad (5)$$

FIG. 1. $\frac{\sin \Delta k u}{\Delta k u}$ plotted vs. $\Delta k u$.

In terms of the refractive indices,

$$\Delta k = \frac{\omega}{c} \left[2n_2 - (n_1 \hat{\mathbf{k}}_1 + n'_1 \hat{\mathbf{k}}'_1) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}_2 \right]. \quad (6)$$

Fig. 1 illustrates the dependence of the square of the factor of eq. (5) (describing the harmonic intensity) on Δk .

2. Phase Matching and the Index Ellipsoid

When phase matching is done in birefringent (i.e. optically anisotropic) materials, the direction of propagation and polarization of the fundamental and 2nd harmonic waves (and their frequency) determine their respective refractive indices. Under the approximations of low efficiency SHG with linearly polarized plane waves which lead to the oscillating factor of eq. (5), the harmonic field exiting the medium is then a function of the directions of propagation via eq. (5).

More explicitly, the two allowed directions of polarization and their respective refractive indices, for a given direction of propagation, are determined by the index ellipsoid of Fig. 2. In type I (OOE) SHG in a uniaxial crystal (as in KDP, whose 1st order susceptibility contains only completely off-diagonal nonzero terms [Appendix A]), $n_1 \hat{\mathbf{k}}_1 = n'_1 \hat{\mathbf{k}}'_1 = n_o^{(\omega)} \hat{\mathbf{k}}_2$ and $n_2 = n_e^{(2\omega)}(\theta)$ in eq. (5). Phase matching is then achieved at the propagation angle that matches the o- and e-indices of refraction at the fundamental and 2nd harmonic frequencies respectively.

3. Reflection and Refraction

In a practical nonlinear experiment, unless both the production of the fundamental(s) and the detection of the generated wave take place inside the nonlinear medium, the behavior of waves at discontinuous boundaries are important.

In line with the treatment of 2nd order effects as coupling perturbations in the 1st order waves (subsection

B. 1.), these boundary conditions become analogous to those for waves in isotropic media. However, the indices of refraction in the nonlinear anisotropic medium are now dependent on the angle of propagation and the polarization, in addition to the frequency. (Numerical calculation is often required if the angle of propagation in the anisotropic medium is unknown.)

For reference and calculations, we have used Nikogosyan et al.'s[11] explicit relations for the angles of refraction and coefficients of reflection at the surface of a uniaxial crystal.

D. (Simplified) Non-Planar Wave SHG

First, consider the case of plane wave sum frequency generation (SFG). The 2nd order polarization of eq. (2) contains a product of exponential phases, which result in a plane wave with the sum of the two original (pump) wavevectors and frequencies. A special case of the summing of these wavevectors occurs in the SHG theory of subsection C. 1.

This summing may be described as the conservation of momentum between the two initial photons and the resultant photon. Qualitatively, from this viewpoint SHG is the process of annihilating two fundamental photons of frequency ω and creating a third of frequency 2ω . As long as the sum of the wavevectors of the two pump photons is a phase matched wavevector, many of these interactions will contribute significantly to the creation of the 2nd harmonic output.

In this way, a beam of light containing photons with a spectrum of wavevectors can be, in say KDP, partially phase matched at a range of angles of propagation relative relative to the optic axis, meaning SHG with a focused laser beam is still practical and also less sensitive to the precise angle of propagation[10] (Ch. 4.9).

FIG. 2. An index ellipsoid for the case of a uniaxial crystal ($n_{x'} = n_{y'} = n_o$). For coherent waves propagating in the direction of \mathbf{k} , the allowed ordinary and extraordinary polarizations and their respective refractive indices are given by the axes of the ellipse perpendicular to \mathbf{k} .

FIG. 3. Schematic diagram of the layout of components. (The neutral density filters were for adjusting the fundamental intensity entering the crystal, but were not used.)

FIG. 4. A photo of the setup on the optical table. The diffraction grating was used in place of the prism for measurements.

III. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

A. Setup

For our measurements, the beam from a 1040 nm pulsed fiber laser was focused into a 0.5 mm long KDP crystal for type I (OOE) SHG. The output was collimated and then sent through a 45° reflector, through an e-direction polarizer, and onto a reflective diffraction grating in order to separate the fundamental IR from the 520 nm 2nd harmonic beam. The diffracted harmonic beam proceeded through a light baffle and onto a photodiode connected in parallel with a resistor and a digital multimeter (DMM) measuring voltage. Fig. 3 shows this setup schematically, and Fig. 4 is a photo of our setup taken during measurements.

The resulting voltage signal for the 2nd harmonic was measured versus the angle of incidence of the fundamental on the crystal relative to the crystal face normal. All components were approximately in the same horizontal plane, and the vertical crystal face was rotated on a vertical axis passing through its center (while all other components were fixed). Positive angles represent an increase in angle of propagation relative to the optic axis.

FIG. 5. 2nd harmonic generation occurring at the crystal.

We used a Kphotonics mode-locked fiber laser which produced 1040 nm pulses with a full-width-half-maximum duration of 150 fs, at a repetition rate of 8 MHz, and at an average power of 40 mW. (These measurements were done by Cromy et al. and listed by them in Ref. [12].) The beam exiting the laser was approximately collimated, with a spot size around 4 mm. The beam was focused by the first lens to maximum intensity in the crystal (on the order of 10 cm or 20 cm away for the two lenses used respectively). The focused beam spot diameter was of the order of 0.1 mm. The KDP crystal was manufactured by Cleveland Crystals, Inc. with a 44.2° cut angle for type I SHG (see Appendix A for properties of KDP). Its length was 0.5 mm and its face size was much larger than the focused beam.

On exiting the crystal, the fundamental and green harmonic beams were collimated again and then passed through a piece of glass coated to reflect ≈ 1000 μm wavelength light incident at $\approx 45^\circ$ (the angle of the reflector was tuned to reject the most overall signal from the fundamental and harmonic). The transmitted green and leftover IR beams were passed through a Glan-Taylor prism polarizer accepting e-polarized (horizontal) light only. Finally, the beams were diffracted, passed through a light baffle, and entered a silicon-based photodiode. The angle of the diffraction grating was tuned so that, of the multiple diffracted green beams, the one with least coinciding IR was incident on the photodiode. (No signal from this diffracted beam was visible on any IR cards, while the green itself still appeared to be on the order of 1 mW in power.) The photodiode had a diameter of ≈ 1 cm and was large enough to capture nearly all of the incident green beam. Its output was connected across a resistor (2.354 ± 0.0005 M Ω) in order to achieve a linear voltage response to intensity at the levels of intensity being received.

Fig. 5 is a photo of SHG occurring in the setup.

B. Incident Angle Measurements and Signal Uncertainties

1. Incident Angle Measurements

Three methods were used to measure the incident angle of the IR beam relative to the crystal face normal, which we label A, B and C.

In method A, angle markings on the crystal mount's rotation stage were used. The markings were 2° apart, leading to a random error of $\approx 0.5^\circ$. The crystal also had to be aligned by eye to the rotation stage, so that there was a systematic error in the readings from the angle markings of $\approx 1^\circ$.

In methods B and C, the harmonic beam reflected from the crystal was used to measure the angle of incidence of the fundamental. A screen with distance measurements was mounted to the optical table in front of the crystal to catch the reflected harmonic, and the angle of the crystal was resolved using the setup geometry. Since the laser, crystal and screen were all mounted to the optical table, the errors in setup geometry and resulting angle measurements in methods B and C became negligible in comparison to the uncertainties in the 2nd harmonic signal.

In method B, a screen with 1/4" spaced markings was used, while in method C, a ruler with 1/32" spaced markings was mounted and used as a screen to allow finer precision.

Additionally, methods A and B used a lens of shorter focal length, the beam was less focused and of lower intensity in the crystal, and the crystal's optic axis was aligned horizontally. In method C, a lens of longer focal length was used which focused the beam to a higher intensity in the crystal, producing more overall 2nd harmonic output. The crystal's optic axis, however, was not carefully aligned and may have been rotated about the face normal. The effects of the rate of convergence of the beam and the alignment of the optic axis is accounted for later in the theoretical fits.

2. 2nd Harmonic Signal Uncertainties

The average power of the IR output from the laser varied $\approx 5\%$ to 10% in periods of time on the order of 1 minute; see Fig. 6. In order to account for this variation, data for a given angle needed to be taken at different points in time spread over periods minutes long. Otherwise, the estimated uncertainties in the signal would not capture the much larger variations over time.

In the data of methods A and B, only one "pass" over angles was done, so that the data from each angle did not capture any variation over time. In method C, two passes were done. Combined, they better represent the order of magnitude of the actual uncertainty in our signal measurements.

FIG. 6. Laser ("Mona") output vs. time running. (The sudden large transitions in output were significant enough to be noticed and accounted for.)

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Theoretical Fitting

A theoretical curve with 3 free parameters was fit to each set of data. The 3 parameters were crystal optic axis misalignment/horizontal axis shift (for method C/methods A and B respectively), beam spread, and overall curve normalization. The theoretical curve was calculated numerically in Python, based on the 4 total parameters mentioned above, the theory discussed in section II, and some additional approximations. We now describe this process in more detail.

For plane wave SHG in KDP, the dependence of the 2nd harmonic signal on angle was assumed to be described by eq. (5) with Δk given by eq. (6) and the index ellipsoid as discussed in subsection 2. The angle of incidence on the crystal face was related to the angle of propagation in the crystal relative to the optic axis by taking into account refraction, the cut angle of the crystal face, and the rotation of the crystal in its mount about the axis normal to its face. Reflection coefficients for the harmonic reflection at the back face of the crystal and the fundamental at the front face were multiplied to the result here. The fundamental reflection coefficient was squared since the harmonic intensity depends on the square of the fundamental intensity.

Using this result for plane waves, we approximated the final experimental situation as an integral of contributions from incident fundamental plane waves, of uniform intensity, evenly distributed about a small square range of solid angle between $\theta' = \theta \pm \alpha$ and $\phi' = \pm \frac{\alpha}{\sin \theta}$. α describes the theoretical angular spread in the beam.

The fitting process was carried out in the Jupyter Notebook environment (Python 3). For each set of data, guesses were made first for the 3 free parameters (the

FIG. 7. Data and fit for method C, averaging values from both passes of measurements. Fit parameters: $\theta_R=21.5^\circ$, $\theta_S=0^\circ$, $\alpha=1.13^\circ$, $N=0.892$. $P(\chi^2)=52\%$. Relative background signal: 3.03%. (Notation: θ_R =crystal rotation misalignment [about axis normal to face; when $\theta_R=0$, optic axis is in the horizontal plane], θ_S =shift of fit along horizontal axis, α =angular size of theoretical (square) beam spread, N =overall fit normalization.)

crystal optic axis misalignment and the horizontal axis shift were always kept at zero for methods A/B and method C respectively). Then, each parameter was adjusted (by the Python script) to minimize the χ^2 value of the fit in repeating succession until changes in the parameters became negligible.

For the data of methods A and B the uncertainties are unknown (due to the variation in laser output over time; see preceding subsection) and are assumed to be uniform. For the data of method C, the more accurate uncertainties estimated from the combination of the two passes of measurements are used in the χ^2 value for fitting.

B. Results and Discussion

Figs. 7-11 show the final data and fitted theoretical curves. The fitted parameters are also listed. We list χ^2 probabilities for method C based on the data and uncertainties used for fitting.

The data of Figs. 10 and 11 for methods A and B is noisier and does not fit as well to the theoretical curve as the data from method C. The need to take the laser output's variation over time into account is confirmed, since the latter measurements were all done over longer periods of time. Specifically, Fig. 7, accounting best for the laser's output variation by averaging 2 passes of measurements, fits remarkably well. (As an alternative solution, the output power of the laser may be measured in real time and used to calibrate the harmonic signal, as was done by Abdel-Halim[13].)

Focusing on Figs. 7-9, showing data of method C, we see that the theoretical curve is a reasonable predictor of the actual signal dependence on the fundamental angle of incidence. The χ^2 probabilities confirm the goodness of fits.

With the assumption that the theoretical curves are reasonably accurate, we use them to estimate the relative average background radiation signal by averaging the differences between the actual signal and the theo-

FIG. 8. Data and fit for method C, 1st pass only. Fit parameters: $\theta_R=21.2^\circ$, $\theta_S=0^\circ$, $\alpha=1.16^\circ$, $N=0.865$. $P(\chi^2)=39\%$. Relative background signal: 3.5%.

retical value over all data points not used in the fitting process (i.e. data for angles outside of the phase matched region). The results are also listed under Figs. 7-11.

The values of all fitted parameters are reasonable. The average estimated angular spread of the beam in method C (using the 2nd focusing lens) is $(1.13 \pm 0.03)^\circ$, corresponding to a beam spread rate of about 2 mm per meter. The horizontal axis shifts of the fits of methods A and B are within the uncertainties in the angle measurements estimated for those methods. The crystal misalignment angles found from the fits of method C, with an average of $(21.5 \pm 0.3)^\circ$, are also within expected values, if not slightly larger.

Since the fundamental was more tightly focused for the measurements of method C, the SHG efficiency and harmonic signal relative to any transmitted fundamental power is expected to be greater. The relative background radiation estimated for methods A and B, $(10 \pm 1)\%$, is significantly larger than the $(3.2 \pm 0.2)\%$ estimated for method C, agreeing with the expectation.

1. Discrepancies

The fitted values for the crystal misalignment angles of method C (Figs. 7-9) are of reasonable order of magnitude but still fairly large. The crystal optic axis was not carefully aligned to the horizontal plane, but the deviation was not expected to be as great as 21° .

The temperature dependences of the indices of refraction have been neglected so far, but they may play a role in this discrepancy. Rather than the crystal optic axis being significantly misaligned, the change in refractive indices and corresponding phase matching conditions due to a temperature change may have caused a larger difference in peak signal angles and fitted values. The temperature change in the crystal could have resulted from absorption of the fundamental beam.

The fitted angular spreads in the fundamental beam do not show any significant change between methods A/B and method C, even though a smaller spread was expected for method C since the beam was focused over a longer distance and to greatest intensity in the crystal (a Gaussian beam is least convergent/divergent near

FIG. 9. Data and fit for method C, 2nd pass only. Fit parameters: $\theta_R=21.8^\circ$, $\theta_S=0^\circ$, $\alpha=1.11^\circ$, $N=0.922$. $P(\chi^2)=41\%$. Relative background signal: 3.2%.

its focus point). The spreads were estimated assuming a uniform rather than Gaussian beam profile, however.

For reference, the values for the o- and e-polarized refractive indices in KDP (Appendix A) give a theoretical phase matched angle of 49.1° (for the direction of propagation in the crystal relative to the optic axis). Refraction causes the theoretical phase matched incident angles to be larger than $(49.1 - 44.2 = 4.9)^\circ$, as does any misalignment in the rotation of the crystal.

V. CONCLUSION

The dependence of 2nd harmonic intensity on angle of incidence of the fundamental beam in a 0.5 mm long KDP crystal was measured using a 1040 nm pulsed fiber laser. The measurements were fit to curves predicted by simplified fundamental theory of nonlinear optics. The fit was good for the most accurate set of data taken (method C, Figs. 7-9) and reasonable for all data. The data and their theoretical curves are shown in Figs. 7-11.

These results may help to provide an insight into the

extent to which simple approximations of 2nd harmonic generation and its generalizations hold for experimental and practical uses. In addition, the specific process of SHG and measurement carried out has been shown to be useful for making practical measurements of the relative intensity of beams of a certain frequency and polarization generated by nonlinear crystals as well as of the linear anisotropic properties of the crystal itself.

As an example, note that of the free parameters in the fitted curves (section IV. A.), only the crystal misalignment and horizontal axis shift affect the peak of the distribution significantly. In a hypothetical case where the measurements of method C were done with a correctly mounted crystal with its optic axis in the horizontal plane, both of these parameters are known to be 0. In this case, the peak of the fit depends only on the o- and e- indices of refraction, and these refractive indices in KDP could be predicted from the measurements and their fit.

Limitations in measuring the absolute intensities of the fundamental and harmonic beam, however, prevent investigation of nonlinear optical properties of the crystal,

FIG. 10. Data and fit for method B (single pass of measurements). Fit parameters: $\theta_R=0^\circ$, $\theta_S=-0.598^\circ$, $\alpha=1.08^\circ$, $N=0.840$. Relative background signal: 9.3%.

FIG. 11. Data and fit for method A (single pass of measurements). Fit parameters: $\theta_R=0^\circ$, $\theta_S=-0.696^\circ$, $\alpha=1.17^\circ$, $N=0.984$. Relative background signal: 10.8%.

such as its 2nd order susceptibilities, unless other methods are used to measure these intensities.

VI. APPENDIX A: KDP PROPERTIES

Nonlinear properties of KDP are listed in Table 1. Values are from Ref. [14].

VII. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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Material Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KDP)

λ_ω	1064 nm
n_ω	$n^o = 1.494$ $n^e = 1.460$
$n_{2\omega}$	$n^o = 1.512$ $n^e = 1.471$
d	$d_{36} = d_{\text{eff}} = 0.43 \text{ pm/V}$ $d_{14} = d_{25} = \text{nonzero}$

TABLE I. Nonlinear optical properties of KDP.

Thanks to Neil Oh for the IR card, and to Orkhongua Batjargal for the Glan-Taylor polarizer.

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